

Calibration of DC measuring systems under railway-like LF dynamic signals

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Abstract — This paper proposes new approaches for the calibration of DC measuring systems under low frequency dynamic current signals and non-stationary AC conditions as usually observed in railway systems.

Index Terms — Dynamic signals, low frequency, efficiency measurement, traceability, urban transport.

I. INTRODUCTION

E-TRENY (Enhanced Traceable Metrology for Energy Efficiency in DC Railway Systems) is a European research project aimed at improving energy efficiency in DC railway and urban transit systems, where a significant portion of regenerative braking energy is lost due to unidirectional substations [1]. While CENELEC/TR 50646 [2] defines specifications for reversible DC substations, standardization gaps remain in their effective characterization. Currently, AC/DC and DC/DC converters are tested under ideal factory conditions or through simulations.

The project develops traceable metrological methods to accurately assess energy efficiency and losses in advanced DC supply solutions, such as bidirectional substations and energy storage systems, under real operating conditions. This includes on-site measurement techniques and calibration infrastructures for high-voltage and high-current systems. To ensure traceability for such measurements, the paper presents two methods for characterizing DC current sensors and measuring systems under low frequency (LF) dynamic signals up to 1000 A, with time scales ranging from hundreds of milliseconds to a few seconds.

III. TEST BED SIGNAL

The typical electrical waveforms occurring in DC railway systems have a behavior very different from pure constant waveforms used in the calibration of measuring systems. An example of DC current behavior is provided in Fig. 1, illustrating the feedback current from a 1.5 kV metro system to the 15 kV AC grid. The current shows a constant slew-rate of about 62.5 A/s with different duration for recovery event. With the aim of reproducing similar waveforms, a periodic triangular shape has been chosen for the calibration.

Fig. 1. Time behaviour of actual DC current signal.

Considering a constant slew-rate with different time-duration of the event, it has been detected a frequency variability from 0.05 Hz to 10 Hz.

IV. APPROACHES FOR NEW TYPE OF CALIBRATIONS

Two independent approaches were developed and described below.

A. Programmable reference generator

The proposed setup for the calibration of a current measuring system (DUT) involves a digital-to-analog converter (DAC) reference function generator supplying a transconductance amplifier that provides the reference dynamic current.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the setup for the generation of reference dynamic current.

The measurand of the calibration stage is the calibration coefficient (1) defined as the ratio between the current incremental ratio provided by the DUT $\left(\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta t}\right)_{DUT}$ over the incremental ratio generated by the reference system $\left(\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta t}\right)_{REF}$. The last one can be expressed as the ratio between the traceable input quantity $\left(\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t}\right)_{REF}$ and the gain of the transconductance amplifier G_{REF} (A/V).

$$C = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta I}{\Delta t}\right)_{DUT}}{\left(\frac{\Delta V}{\Delta t}\right)_{REF} G_{REF}} \quad (1)$$

The quantity G_{REF} is obtained by a preliminary calibration stage shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Setup for the calibration of the transconductance gain G_{REF}

The function generator produces the step-voltage waveform, the amplifier transforms it in a step current which is measured through calibrated shunt (R_{sh}) and multimeter (DMM). Two synchronized DMM, operating in DC voltage mode and triggered by the function generator, measure the DC voltage at each step. The average behavior of the amplifier gain can be computed as:

$$G_{REF} = \frac{1}{R_{sh}N} \sum_{i=0}^N \frac{v_{HP_i}}{v_i} \quad (2)$$

Where v_{HP_i} and v_i are the output and input DC voltage at the i -th step and N is the number of steps.

B. Reference measurement setup

Another approach for the characterization of DC current sensors under dynamic signals relies on a traceable measurement setup shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Schematic diagram of calibration under dynamic currents

The low frequency current generated by software-controlled power source flows simultaneously through the DUT and reference current transducers. Co-axial shunts are connected to the outputs of the transducers to obtain voltage signals as measurands. Two DMMs externally triggered acquire the dynamic voltages. These DMMs are calibrated in the LNE laboratory that ensures their traceability for frequencies lower than 10 Hz. The developed setup might calibrate current transducers under dynamic triangular signals up to 600 A peak value and fundamental frequency from 1 Hz to 10 Hz.

V. RESULTS

The differences between the indications of the DUT and the reference transducer are shown in Table I for 500 A and for three types of calibrations: under DC current; under AC 50 Hz sin-current and under 1 Hz triangular current.

Table I Differences between transducers at 500 A

Frequency (Hz)	Difference
0 (DC)	$1.1 \cdot 10^{-6}$
1 (triangular)	$8.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$
50 (sin)	$-3.0 \cdot 10^{-6}$

It can be observed that the differences between transducers are very low, 10^{-6} order for DC and AC-50 Hz calibrations, while this difference drastically increases at $8.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$ when 1 Hz triangular signal is applied. These results outline a change in the transducer response under dynamic current.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study illustrates the importance of characterizing the current transducers under realistic waveforms and not only under pure DC and AC sinusoidal waveforms. Implementing new types of calibrations based on dynamic currents that reproduce the AC/DC substations signals (similar amplitude and shape) allows obtaining the appropriate corrections for the measurement systems. Therefore, more accurate and reliable calibration could be proposed for on-site measurements. A comparison between the two presented approaches is ongoing.

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